

NDAC/LO/115
Nov 30, 1988

26th NDAC Report from Lund Observatory

WP6000: Step 2/3 (Lindgren)

No work to report for September-November 1988.

WP8000: Double Stars (Söderhjelm)

The main parts of the reduction program for multiple systems (STDMUL) are now working and tested (C). Work has then concentrated on the SEEKDBL program, which will discover unknown doubles with separations 0.1-1 arcsec. Via the $\Delta\chi^2$ discovery criterion, the information-matrices derived in the standard IDT preprocessing have a direct influence on the double-star discovery statistics, and some extra weighting seems necessary in order to get the required 'flat' $\Delta\chi^2$ -histograms for single stars (C). Even after such changes in the IDT preprocessing, different criteria for double-star detection are seen to give different results, and final optimization has to await the real data. The main parts of SEEKDBL are now working and tested for standard 8.5 mag stars (C). Further tests for brighter and fainter systems will soon be available.

Working papers:

- C =NDAC/LO/112 (Söderhjelm, 1988 Sep 8):
HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, VII
- C =NDAC/LO/113 (Söderhjelm, 1988 Oct 18):
Some empirical corrections to the IDT information matrix
- C =NDAC/LO/114 (Söderhjelm, 1988 Nov 18):
HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, VIIIA